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BIOLOGICALLY INACTIVE GROWTH HORMONE SYNDROME IN CHILDREN: DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, AND SOCIAL ADAPTATION (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract

Biologically inactive growth hormone syndrome (BIGHS) is a rare genetically determined pathology characterized by short stature despite normal or elevated growth hormone levels and decreased insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) levels. The article presents a literature review on the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of BIGHS. The importance of early diagnosis using hormonal tests and molecular genetic analysis, which enables timely initiation of recombinant growth hormone therapy and improvement of children's physical and psychoemotional development, is emphasized. The article also considers the peculiarities of the social adaptation of patients with this pathology.

Keywords: *biologically inactive growth hormone syndrome, short stature, somatotropin, insulin-like growth factor-1, diagnosis, treatment, social adaptation of children.*

Introduction: Growth disorders in children are a relevant issue in modern endocrinology and pediatrics. One of the rare but important causes of short stature is biologically inactive growth hormone syndrome (BIGHS), a genetically determined condition characterized by isolated somatotropin deficiency despite normal or elevated growth hormone (GH) levels and decreased insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) levels. Early diagnosis of BIGHS is crucial for optimizing treatment and ensuring the social adaptation of affected children.

Etiology and Pathogenesis: BIGHS is caused by mutations in the growth hormone gene, leading to reduced biological activity without affecting hormone secretion. Both hormone-sensitive and hormone-insensitive forms of the syndrome have been identified [3]. GH's biological activity is mediated through the stimulation of IGF-1 synthesis in the liver. In BIGHS, normal or elevated GH levels are observed along with low IGF-1 levels. Ghrelin, which potentiates GH secretion, also plays an important role in the complex pathogenesis of BIGHS [2].

Clinical Presentation: Children with BIGHS have proportionate body structures, often with characteristic facial features such as a prominent forehead, saddle nose, and closely set eyes [3]. In addition to short stature, patients often report headaches, weakness, fatigue, impaired attention and memory, and frequent viral infections. Growth retardation typically exceeds 2 SD below the age norm, with a low growth rate (1–4 cm/year). The syndrome significantly impacts psychoemotional health, contributing to low self-esteem, a predisposition to depressive disorders, and difficulties in social adaptation [1].

Diagnosis: BIGHS diagnosis is based on hormonal testing showing normal or elevated GH levels in pharmacological stimulation tests, accompanied by low

IGF-1 levels [2,3]. A key diagnostic tool is the four-day GH sensitivity test, which reveals more than a two-fold increase in IGF-1 levels [3]. In complex cases, molecular genetic testing is recommended to detect mutations in the GH gene.

Treatment: The main treatment approach is the administration of recombinant growth hormone (rGH) at a dose of 0.033–0.05 mg/kg/day [3]. Early initiation of therapy improves growth response outcomes. In cases of early or precocious puberty, a combination of rGH with gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogues (GnRHa) is used to extend the growth period and improve final height [1,2]. Thyroid and adrenal functions are typically preserved, but regular monitoring during therapy is required.

Prognosis and Social Adaptation: With timely diagnosis and appropriate treatment, children with BIGHS can achieve normal or near-normal final height [1–3]. Treatment also positively affects the psychoemotional state and social adaptation, reducing the risk of inferiority complex and social maladaptation.

Conclusions: Biologically inactive growth hormone syndrome is a rare but significant cause of short stature in children. Comprehensive evaluation including GH and IGF-1 measurements and sensitivity testing is required for diagnosis. Treatment with recombinant GH, combined with GnRHa when necessary, substantially improves growth outcomes and psychosocial adaptation. Early detection and management are key to ensuring normal physical and emotional development in affected children.

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